

PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CONSTRUCTION AND OPERATING ENTERPRISES IN THE CONTEXT OF ECONOMIC MODERNIZATION

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Abstract. The article emphasizes the main participants of construction in the context of economic modernization. At the same time, the production process in construction can be organized in various forms and methods, with particular attention paid to the contract method, the economic method and other methods.

Key words: Construction network, construction complex, construction process. construction product.

Investors, customers, builders, contractors and designers participate in capital construction as the main participants of the investment process according to their duties.

An investor is a subject of investment activity that finances the construction of an object with private or debt funds. The investor has full legal rights to dispose of the investment results.

It also determines the form of attracting investments (capital investments), develops the terms of construction contracts, implements financial and credit relations with the participants of the investment process. An investor is a customer, creditor, buyer of construction products, and also performs the function of a direct builder.

The customer is a legal or physical person who has assumed the functions

of the organizer and manager of the construction of the object in the period from the development of the technical and economic basis to the commissioning of the object or the beginning of the production capacity of the object.

The construction owner is a legal or physical person who has the right to own the land area under construction. Unlike the customer, he uses the land area allocated for construction under the terms of a long-term lease.

The contractor (main contractor) is a construction company that is carrying out the construction of the facility based on the contract. The general contractor is fully responsible to the customer for the results of the construction in accordance with the terms of the contract. It may engage subcontractors to perform certain types of work when necessary

The designer is a design organization or other similar institution that designs the future construction of this or that object based on the contract concluded with the customer. The developer is fully responsible for the quality of the project and its underlying technical and economic indicators. The customer establishes authorship control to monitor compliance with the solutions provided for in the project.

The process of construction production can be organized in various forms and methods, including the contract method, the economic method, turnkey delivery and sale of objects.

Contractual construction is carried out by regular construction organizations (firms) based on contracts concluded with customers. This is the main and most common method of construction. Today, more than 80 percent of all contract work in the field of capital construction is carried out in this way. "Capital construction contract" serves as the basis for its implementation.

Construction of objects or construction-assembly, repair-construction works in the economic method is carried out at the expense of the efforts and funds of economic subjects - enterprises, organizations, institutions and the like.

Renovation and expansion of enterprises, smaller construction objects, improvement of areas and rooms, repair works are often carried out in this way.

In the transfer of objects to full completion ("turnkey" handover), the functions of the customer are transferred to the general contractor, who starts construction from the beginning and hands over the object to the customer in a partially completed state. This method of construction is very common in housing construction.

In addition to the forms indicated above, there are organizational forms of construction, such as specialization, concentration, cooperation, from the point of view of social division of labor. It should also be mentioned that these forms are used not only in construction, but also in other sectors of the national economy, first of all, in industry. Experience shows that by skillfully using these forms, it is possible to achieve high efficiency in production and capital investments. For example, if specialization and cooperation allow to reduce costs and improve the quality of products, concentration and combination lead to the integrated use of raw materials and materials and further expansion of the scope of scientific and technical development in the field of construction.

As a branch of material production, construction not only produces products, but also consumes or uses resources of one kind or another for this. According to the available data, 80 percent of the products of the building materials industry, about half of the wood materials, more than 20 percent of the rolled metal, and more than 10 percent of the products of the engineering industry are used in construction. The value of transport costs is 20-25 percent of construction costs. In other words, construction is served by almost all branches of the national economy.

The building materials industry occupies a special place in the development of the material and technical base of construction. Enterprises in this sector produce cement, lime, plaster, brick, glass, coating and heat-insulating materials,

various fillers.

The relative share of the consumption of certain types of materials in capital construction is very large. For example, about 80 percent of cement, window glass - 50 percent, wooden materials - 35-40 percent, rolled ferrous metals - 20 percent, soft covering materials - almost 70 percent are consumed.

The most complete supply of construction materials, structures, techniques and other means of production depends to a large extent on the perfection and further development of inter-industry relations. This is usually reflected in the intersectoral balance of production and the distribution of products in the national economy.

The transition from command, centralized management and planning to the market system in the economy has opened wide opportunities for economic entities to develop construction and strengthen its material and technical base, in which the role of regional management bodies is becoming stronger. But this does not mean that the development and strengthening of the construction production base will happen spontaneously. It should be in accordance with the scientific principles of development and deployment of the material and technical base of construction and its full provision of resources.

For the development and placement of the material and technical base of construction, it is necessary to have methods that allow quantitative expression of all factors and conditions that affect the selection of the construction area and place. Such methods are mathematical models that allow finding the optimal solution to a problem. One of them is linear programming, which combines the theory and practice of solving extreme problems in which it is required to find the given linear constraints of variables and the set of values that maximize or minimize the objective function of these variables.

In the formation of the economic-mathematical model of the optimal development and placement of the material and technical base of construction,

along with other factors, it is necessary to take into account the points of production of raw materials and materials, the points where enterprises can be located, the volume of production at these points, transportation costs, etc. In this case, the criterion for the optimal solution of the problem is usually that the product to be produced in the future is highly competitive, and at the same time, the costs (one-time and current) in creating and deploying the enterprise are as low as possible.

One of the important conditions for the further development of the material and technical base of construction is the improvement of mutual relations between the enterprises of the construction industry and the scientific and research organizations involved in the design of enterprises that produce construction structures, details and materials.

In this case, the following should be the basis of these mutual relations:

- development of new, most cost-effective projects of construction industry enterprises with highly mechanized and automated production processes;

- choosing the optimal options for placing these enterprises in the territory of the country, taking into account the rational schemes of the transportation of raw materials and materials, constructions and the development of cooperation in production;

- technical re-equipment of existing enterprises, primarily those that have been operating for 20-30 years or longer.

By developing their material and technical bases, construction industry enterprises and organizations not only strengthen their production potential, but also ensure their economic stability in a competitive environment and shorten the life cycles of their activities. In this case, the development of the material and technical base does not consist only of the absolute growth of the technical or material supply of production, or, in the words of economists, the increase of the supply of funds, but is carried out on the basis of its priority principles, on the

basis of the principle of ensuring maximum efficiency.

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